

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370049383>

Why Japan's politics matter?

Article · April 2023

CITATIONS

0

READS

349

1 author:

[Shabib Md Shadakatul Baree](#)

University of Dhaka

9 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Blue Economy and Bangladesh: Challenges, Prospects and Possibilities [View project](#)

Why Japan's politics matter?

Introduction: Japan is a leading player in global affairs. The country's politics and policies have a significant impact on global politics and economy and its influence extends far beyond its borders. As such, Japan's politics have a considerable impact on global affairs, especially in areas such as trade, security, and diplomacy.

Economic Powers of Japan:

Japan is the third-largest economy in the world, with a GDP of over \$5 trillion. It is a significant player in the global economy and a major trading partner for many countries and so its policies and actions have a significant effect on global affairs. Japan's role in global finance is also significant. Japan is the second-largest holder of foreign exchange reserves globally, and its yen is a significant currency in international finance.

Japan's politics and Global trade :

Japan has long been an important player in global foreign trade. This has been true since the late 19th century, when the Meiji Restoration opened Japan to the world, launching a period of economic growth and modernization. Today, Japan is the 4th largest exporter and 5th largest importer of goods and services in the world, making it a significant player in global foreign trade.

Japan's economic success has been largely attributed to its strong international trade relationships. Japan has a diverse economy with a multitude of trading partners, including the United States, China, South Korea, and the European Union. Japan is a major supplier of key resources including food and fuel, and is a major purchaser of electronic components, machinery, and chemical products. As such, Japan is critical to the global supply chain for many industries.

In addition to its export and import activities, Japan has become an active participant in international trade negotiations. In recent years, Japan has been involved in the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) and the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) negotiations, both of which seek to liberalize trade between member nations. These agreements will have far-reaching implications for Japan and the world at large.

Japan is a key member of Asia-Pacific Economic Co-operation (APEC), and its participation in the organization has been very active. Japan has placed a priority on regional economic integration and trade liberalization, and it has worked to promote investment and infrastructure development within the region. Japan has also played an important role in facilitating the development of regional economic policies and projects, such as the APEC Investment Facilitation Action Plan.

Japan's membership in the TPP and APEC has helped to improve its global standing and give it an important voice in global affairs. Its position in the TPP and APEC also gives it an important role in global trade and economic relations. As a member of both organizations, Japan has a greater say in setting the rules and regulations that govern international trade.

Finally, Japan has become a major investor in overseas markets. The country has invested extensively in foreign markets, particularly in Asia. These investments have helped to promote economic growth and development in the region while also providing Japan with a valuable source of income.

Japan's foreign investment:

Japan is the world's third-largest economy and is a major source of foreign investment. Japanese companies invest heavily in other countries, primarily in the form of direct investment, mergers and acquisitions, joint ventures and strategic alliances. As of 2018, the total value of Japan's foreign direct investment outflows surpassed \$1 trillion. Japan's foreign investment is focused on the US, China, and Southeast Asia, but it has also been expanding in India and other parts of Asia, Latin America, and Africa.

Japanese companies have become increasingly active in foreign markets, often investing in sectors such as infrastructure, natural resources, telecommunications, banking, and manufacturing. This has allowed Japan to strengthen its economic ties with countries around the world, as well as to gain access to new markets and technologies. Japanese companies are also increasingly investing in emerging markets, allowing them to tap into new sources of growth and potential.

Foreign investment is also important in terms of international cooperation and the promotion of global development. Japan's foreign investment helps to create jobs and economic growth in host countries. Japan is one of the biggest foreign investors in the world, investing in over 80 countries. The top 10 countries that receive the most foreign investment from Japan include the United States, China, the United Kingdom, Australia, France, South Korea, India, Germany, Brazil and Bangladesh. In Bangladesh, Japanese foreign investment has been largely concentrated in the power and energy sector, with investments in a range of projects including a liquefied natural gas (LNG) power plant, a 1000 MW coal-fired plant, and an offshore wind farm. Japan has also been involved in infrastructure projects such as a deep seaport, a new airport and a bus rapid transit system in Bangladesh. In addition, Japan has invested in Bangladesh's manufacturing sector, with investments in electronics, automotive and textile industries. Japan is also a major investor in the financial services sector in Bangladesh, and has provided the country with credit lines and development assistance to support its financial sector. The Japanese government has also been active in supporting Bangladesh's agricultural sector, providing technology and capital investments to help improve productivity and quality. Japan is also a major donor to Bangladesh's health and education sectors, providing funding for a range of initiatives such as school and hospital construction and infrastructure improvements. Japanese companies have also been investing in Bangladesh's IT and digital technology sectors, providing funding

Japan's foreign investment has been a major driving force of its economic growth. According to the Japanese Ministry of Finance, as of 2019, the total amount of foreign direct investment (FDI) received by Japan from other countries reached ¥19.5 trillion (approximately \$180 billion). This is a significant increase from ¥6.2 trillion in 2010, and is a testament to the growing importance of foreign investment to the Japanese economy.

The largest FDI contributor to Japan is the United States, which has invested ¥3.9 trillion in Japanese firms as of 2019. Other top contributors include China (¥2.5 trillion), the United Kingdom (¥1.9 trillion), South Korea (¥1.6 trillion), and Germany (¥1.4 trillion).

In terms of investment direction, the largest portion of FDI invested in Japan is directed towards manufacturing, making up approximately 40% of the total FDI. This is followed by the finance and insurance sector, real estate activities, and professional, scientific and technical activities.

The increase in foreign investment has been a boon for the Japanese economy, as it has helped the country increase its competitiveness, attract more talent and technology, and diversify its economy. Additionally, it has increased the number of jobs available in the country and spurred innovation.

Japan's Global Donation Program :

Japan is a major donor of development aid and humanitarian assistance to countries in need, providing a significant amount of assistance to countries in need. Japan's foreign aid program known as Japan's official Development Assistance is one of the world's largest, providing billions of dollars to assist countries in need in times of disaster, poverty, and other developmental areas.

The Japanese government has a long history of providing assistance to countries in need. Japan began providing assistance after World War II, when it received billions of dollars in aid from the United States and other countries. Since then, Japan has been one of the world's leading providers of development aid and humanitarian assistance. This has included providing assistance to countries affected by natural disasters, such as the 2004 Asian tsunami, as well as assistance to countries affected by conflicts and civil wars, such as Syria.

Japan's foreign aid program is focused on promoting economic and social development within recipient countries. Japan provides assistance in areas including education, healthcare, infrastructure development, and poverty reduction. It also provides assistance in the form of direct budget support, food aid, and grant programs.

Japan's assistance is an important part of global affairs as it helps to reduce poverty and promote development in recipient countries. This in turn helps to promote global stability and security, as it creates more prosperous and stable countries that are less likely to become sources of conflict.

Japan's Diplomatic relations East asia, Middle east and West :

Japan is an interesting country because of its location. It lies in East Asia, but is also close to the Middle East and the West, making it the gateway between the three regions. This has been used by Japan to its advantage throughout history, allowing it to become an important power in the region.

Japan's strategic position has enabled it to influence the balance of power in East Asia, the Middle East and the West. This is because its policies and decisions can affect the way these regions interact with each other and the way that they are perceived by the rest of the world. For example, if Japan were to strengthen its ties with a particular nation in one of the regions, this could strengthen their overall relationship and lead to more positive outcomes for both countries. Similarly, if Japan were to adopt a more isolationist stance and cut itself off from one of these regions, it could lead to an imbalance in the regional power balance.

Japan's policies also have global implications. Its decision to join the U.S.-led coalition to fight against the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria is one example of how its actions have had an impact on the world stage. Japan's leadership in the fight against terrorism has earned it recognition from the international community and has helped to strengthen its position as a major power in East Asia and the Middle East.

Japan's ability to influence the balance of power in East Asia, the Middle East and the West is particularly important in times of Japan has provided economic assistance and technology to East Asian countries in order to boost their economies and increase their global competitiveness. Japan has also engaged in joint

economic initiatives with countries in the Middle East and the West, including the Middle East Peace Process, the Japan-U.S. Economic Partnership for Growth, and the Japan-U.S. Alliance for Regional Stability.

In addition to its economic power, Japan is also a major military power. The Japan Self-Defense Forces (JSDF) are one of the most technologically advanced militaries in the world, and Japan's defense budget is the fifth largest in the world. As such, Japan has demonstrated its ability to project its military power throughout East Asia and the Middle East in order to maintain regional stability and protect its allies from external threats.

Japan-U.S Alliance

The relationship between Japan and the United States has long been a cornerstone of global affairs. This strategic partnership has spanned decades and has been characterized by trust and cooperation. The two countries have worked together in pursuit of common security and economic interests, resulting in a strong and durable alliance.

The economic relationship between Japan and the United States has been the major focus of the partnership between the two countries. The two nations have long cooperated to promote economic growth and stability in the region. The United States has provided technical and financial support to Japan, while Japan has served as a major source of technology and capital investments. The two countries have also implemented a number of free trade agreements, including the Japan-U.S. Economic Partnership Agreement, which has served to further cement the economic relationship.

In addition to economic cooperation, the two countries have worked together to promote regional security. Japan and the United States have been major partners in the Asia-Pacific region, providing military support to regional allies and taking a leading role in regional security initiatives. The two countries have also worked together to address the threat of nuclear proliferation and to promote non-proliferation and disarmament.

The political relationship between Japan and the United States has been equally important. The two countries have maintained a strong dialogue on a range of issues, from security to economics to human rights. More recently, the two nations have worked together to advance a range of diplomatic initiatives, such as the Trans-Pacific Partnership.

Japan in UN :

Japan is one of the leading countries in the United Nations (UN) and is a major player in global affairs. Japan is the world's third-largest economy, and is often seen as a key ally to the United States, particularly in the Asia-Pacific region. Japan's stance on global issues, such as climate change, disarmament, and economic cooperation, is highly influential in the United Nations and the international community.

Japan is a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council, and is a strong advocate for global peace and stability. Japan has made significant contributions to UN-led peacekeeping and humanitarian missions, and has provided development assistance to developing countries. Japan has long been a major donor to the UN's development arm, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP).

In addition to its financial contributions to the UN, Japan has also taken a leading role in advocating for UN reform, most recently with its successful campaign for a permanent seat on the UN Security Council.

Japan has also been a leader in promoting human rights and has pushed for stronger global action on issues such as gender equality and the rights of indigenous peoples. Japan is also a strong supporter of the International Criminal Court, and has been a major donor to the Court's trust fund.

Japan is also a leading diplomatic power in the United Nations, and is a major contributor to the organization's efforts to tackle global challenges such as climate change, poverty, and pandemics.

Japan in G7 and G20 :

Japan is an important member of both the G7 and G20 groups, which are two of the most influential forums for international dialogue and action on global economic and political issues. This makes Japan a significant player in global affairs.

Japan's presence in the G7 and G20 is a reflection of its growing economic strength. Japan is the world's third largest economy and is a major exporter of goods and services. Its economic importance has earned it a seat at both of these global forums. This gives Japan a major platform to voice its views on global issues and to put forward its proposals for solutions to global problems.

The G7 and G20 forums also provide a platform for Japan to participate in international negotiations on global economic and political issues. Japan has used its position on both of these groups to actively promote its policies and to take part in the dialogue surrounding various global issues. For example, Japan has played an active role in discussions on climate change and free trade, as well as participating in the nuclear negotiations with Iran.

Japan is also a major contributor to international aid and assistance. This is evidenced by its involvement in the G7 and G20 Okinawa Summits, where Japan pledged billions of dollars to support development initiatives in the Asia-Pacific region. Japan also contributes to the fight against poverty through its membership in the G20 Global Partnership for Development, which helps to coordinate development aid to low-income countries.

Japan's nuclear potential :

Japan's nuclear potential has been a major factor in global affairs since the nation first began to develop its nuclear program in the late 1950s. Japan is a signatory of the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty, and has maintained its commitment to remain a non-nuclear weapons state since then. This commitment was further strengthened in the 1970s when Japan declared that it would not develop, produce, or possess nuclear weapons.

At the same time, Japan has been able to remain a powerful presence in global affairs by maintaining its nuclear power infrastructure. Japan is one of the few countries in the world that has a full-scale nuclear power industry, and is currently the world's third-largest producer of nuclear energy. Japan has 54 nuclear reactors, and is the fourth-largest producer of nuclear-generated electricity in the world. This provides Japan with the ability to exert influence in global affairs through the production and sale of nuclear-generated electricity.

Japan's nuclear potential also serves as a deterrent. The nation is well aware of the potential threat posed by its neighbors, North Korea and China, and has maintained a strong nuclear infrastructure as a result of this. This serves to maintain regional stability, as Japan's nuclear capability serves as an effective counterbalance to any potential aggression by its neighbors.

In addition, Japan's commitment to non-proliferation has been an important part of global nuclear arms control efforts. Japan is a party to the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty.

Japan's military power :

The importance of Japan's military for global affairs cannot be overstated. Japan is a major player in the international arena, with a strong economy, an influential culture, and a long-standing commitment to peace and stability. In addition, the country is a key part of the United Nations Security Council, and is often called upon to provide military support to international operations.

The main reasons why Japan's military matters in global affairs is that it provides a stabilizing force in the region and beyond. Japan is one of the few countries in the world with a powerful military and a generous defense budget. The country is a major provider of troops for UN peacekeeping operations, and has contributed to missions in Iraq, Afghanistan, and other areas. In addition, Japan has strong diplomatic relations with the United States, China, and other countries, and is a major player in the East Asian region.

Moreover, Japan's military capabilities are essential for keeping peace in East Asia. The country deploys troops in various international organizations, including the United Nations, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). These deployments help to ensure that international disputes are resolved peacefully, and that regional stability is maintained.

In addition, The Japanese Self-Defense Forces (JSDF) are highly trained and equipped, and it has the capability to protect its interests and the interests of its allies in any conflict.

Japanese innovation and Technology :

Japan is a leader in innovation and technology, with companies like Toyota, Sony, and Honda known worldwide for their cutting-edge products. Japan's advancements in robotics, electronics, and telecommunications have had a significant impact on the global market. The development of advanced technologies, such as robotics and artificial intelligence, are having a major impact on global affairs. Japan is a leader in these technologies, and its progress has implications that reverberate around the world.

Robotics, in particular, is an area in which Japan is particularly strong. Japan already has a significant head start in the field, with robots being deployed in various industries, from construction to agriculture. This is making it easier for Japanese companies to automate labor-intensive processes, allowing them to remain competitive in global markets. As robots become more sophisticated, they will become increasingly capable of doing complex tasks, freeing up human workers to focus on higher value-added activities. This could potentially give Japan an edge in the global economy.

At the same time, Japan's progress in artificial intelligence is having a major impact on global affairs. AI technology is being used to monitor and analyze data, and to automate decision-making processes. This has implications for how governments and businesses operate, and can affect the way decisions are made and resources are allocated. AI is also being used to develop new technologies, such as self-driving cars and smart homes. As Japan continues to advance its AI capabilities, it will become even more influential in terms of global decision-making and resource allocation.

Finally, Japan's progress in robotics and artificial intelligence is leading to the development of new products and services that have the potential to revolutionize the world.

Japanese Soft-power : Japanese Culture

Japan is an important cultural leader in the world and its cultural output can have a significant impact on how other countries view the world. Japan is an influential actor on the global stage and has become a powerful cultural leader due to its strong economy and cultural innovations. Japan is a major economic player, ranking third in the world in terms of GDP. This economic success has allowed Japan to invest in creative industries and to export its culture.

The traditional culture of Japan is highly respected by many countries and acts as a source of inspiration for their own cultures. Japanese art, literature, and music are known for their innovation and creativity. Japanese martial arts, notably Judo and Karate, have also become popular around the world. Overall, the traditional culture of Japan is seen as a source of inspiration for many countries.

But it is the modern forms of Japanese culture that have made the biggest impact. Anime is one of the most successful cultural exports from Japan and has become a global phenomenon. It has been embraced by people of all ages and from all walks of life, inspiring creativity and imagination. Japanese fashion, particularly streetwear, has also had an enormous influence on the world, from high-end fashion to everyday style.

Japanese culture has become a major force in international relations. It has also had a significant impact on the economy, as the huge demand for Japanese products has led to a strong trade relationship between Japan and other countries. Japan's soft power is also significant in global affairs. Japan's popular culture, including anime, manga, and video games, has a global following and has helped shape global cultural trends.

Japan advocating for Global Disarmament and Nuclear non- proliferation :

Japan is a key player in the global movement for disarmament and nuclear non-proliferation. This is because its territory was affected by the devastating consequences of atomic bombs used at the end of World War II. Such experience has served to shape Japan's policy on nuclear weapons and disarmament, with the country taking a strong stance in favor of nuclear disarmament and non-proliferation.

The Japanese Constitution prohibits Japan from possessing, producing, or allowing the introduction of nuclear weapons into its territory. The country is also a party to the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT), which seeks to prevent the spread of nuclear weapons and weapons technology. In the face of escalating global tensions and the nuclear arms race between the USA and Russia, Japan has taken a leadership role advocating for the de-escalation of nuclear tensions, and the global elimination of nuclear weapons.

Japan is also a leader in advocating for the peaceful use of nuclear energy. The country has been using nuclear energy as a source of electricity since the 1960s, and it currently has 54 nuclear reactors operating in the country. The Japanese government is promoting the use of nuclear energy as a clean and safe energy source, with the aim of decreasing Japan's dependence on fossil fuels.

In terms of global affairs, Japan's stance on disarmament and use of nuclear energy has the potential to positively impact global security and the environment.

Japan's politics and climate change :

Japan's politics also have a significant impact on global efforts to combat climate change. This country is a key contributor to the global fight against climate change and the promotion of clean energy. This is important in global affairs because it is a signal to other countries that fighting climate change is a priority, and that they should be taking steps to reduce their emissions and clean up their energy sources. It is also important in global affairs because Japan is a major world power and its actions can influence the decisions of other countries and the international community.

Japan has taken a number of steps to reduce emissions and promote clean energy. The country is the fifth-largest emitter of greenhouse gases globally and has committed to reducing its emissions by 26% by 2030 compared to 2013 levels. Japan is also a member of the Paris Agreement and has been involved in several international initiatives aimed at promoting renewable energy and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. It has also invested billions of dollars in clean energy technology, such as wind and solar power, and has provided financial incentives for companies and citizens to invest in renewable energy. These actions have sent a strong signal to other countries that they should also be taking action to reduce their emissions and switch to renewable energy sources.

Japan's peace keeping effort :

Japan has recently become increasingly involved in global security issues and has contributed significantly to international peacekeeping efforts. This is largely due to the country's commitment to pacifism, which it has maintained since WWII. Japan has been engaged in several security-related activities in recent years. It has increased its defense spending, and the country's Self-Defense Forces have been involved in peacekeeping missions in several countries. Japan has also been working closely with the United States to address regional security issues, including the North Korean nuclear threat.

Japan's pacifism has allowed it to remain active in international affairs above and beyond what is required for its own defense. This has included an increased focus on peacekeeping, humanitarian aid, and other forms of international cooperation. Since the early 2000s, Japan has become a major contributor to international peacekeeping operations, including sending troops to Iraq and Afghanistan to provide humanitarian and reconstruction aid. In addition, Japan has provided a range of support for the UN-led operations in the Democratic Republic of Congo. It has also provided funding for the International Criminal Court, and has provided support for the UN-led interventions in the Central African Republic, South Sudan, and Mali.

Japan's commitment to peacekeeping and international cooperation has also extended beyond the military. Japan has become increasingly active in the development of international legal norms, and has worked to strengthen the international legal framework around issues such as cyber security and the regulation of weapons of mass destruction. This has included providing technical expertise to international organizations and hosting conferences to promote collaboration on international security issues.

Furthermore, Japan has used its diplomatic skills to facilitate negotiations between conflicting parties. This has included providing financial and diplomatic support to peace talks in Syria and the Middle East, and working to broker a ceasefire between Israel.

China's raise make Japan more important :

In some respects, the rise of China makes Japan strategically more important to the United States and to other countries in the Asia Pacific. Japan will play a key role in America's grand strategy of balancing against China. Because of the incipient great power rivalry between China and Japan, Japan will choose balancing against China rather than bandwagoning with it, which makes Japan a suitable partner for America's Asia-Pacific strategy. Japan and the US-Japan alliance are the principal obstacles standing between China and its desire for hegemony in the region. How to deal with a rising China is a strongly shared strategic concern of the United States and Japan, as is a peaceful solution to the Taiwan problem. Japan has also become more important to the United States because South Korea is increasingly seen as a less reliable partner. Japan is now central to US global as well as regional strategic planning, and the alliance is going through a third stage of reaffirmation, redefinition and revitalization. For other states concerned that China might gain hegemony over Asia, Japan is central to preventing China's sphere of influence spreading across the Asian continent. For this reason, resistance from regional states in the Asia-Pacific to Japan's rise will be moderated. They will be less concerned about the growth of Japanese military power than they might be. Japan will become more important as a balancer of China to Southeast Asian countries and to Australia – in other words, to all those countries seeking regional counterweights to Chinese influence. Southeast Asian states, in particular, are concerned to see a diplomatic balance maintained in the region between China and Japan. Too far a tilt in China's direction leaves them exposed to unilateral Chinese influence. The future will see the emergence of Sino-Japanese rivalry for influence in East Asia and the wider Asia-Pacific region. Chinese actions and policies towards ASEAN will both mirror and reflect Japanese policies and vice versa. The China factor has already been observable in shaping Japan's policies towards signing a Free Trade Agreement with ASEAN. Japan quickened the pace of its negotiations in response to China's getting a head start in talks on such an agreement. China's potential as a dominant player in any future East Asian integration will only serve further to encourage Japan's striving to play an equivalent role in encouraging and supporting this integration.

Conclusion: Japan's politics have a considerable impact on global affairs, given its position as one of the world's most advanced and technologically sophisticated countries. The country's trade policies, security initiatives, diplomacy, technological advancements, and efforts to combat climate change are all critical to global peace, stability, and economic growth. As such, Japan's politics must continue to play a crucial role in addressing global challenges and promoting international cooperation.